

MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATION OF MOLECULAR INTERACTIONS BETWEEN SWNT AND EPOXY RESIN MOLECULES OF NANOCOMPOSITE PROCESSING

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ABSTRACT: In the processing of nanotube-reinforced composites, nanotube-resin wetting/impregnation and interfacial bonding will happen at the nanoscale or molecular level. Understanding these interactions is crucial for nanoscale processing modeling and resin matrix selection in developing single-walled nanotube (SWNT)/polymer composites. In this research, molecular dynamics (MD) simulation technique was employed to reveal the molecular interactions between (10,10) SWNTs and two epoxy resin matrices during the wetting or impregnation in composite processing. The two resin systems studied were Epon 862 resin/EPI-CURE W curing agent and DGEBA (diglycidylether of bisphenol A) resin/diethylenetriamine (DETA) curing agent. The simulation results revealed that all molecules of the selected resins and curing agents had a tendency to stretch and wrap around the SWNT surfaces, which indicated possible good tube/resin bonding in the resultant nanocomposites. MD simulation of SWNT pullout from cured Epon 862 resin/EPI-CURE W matrix was also conducted. The interfacial shear strength is as high as 75MPa based on the interaction energy calculated from the pullout simulation. Nanostructures of SWNT/Epon 862 composites were also observed and compared with the MD simulation results in the research.

KEY WORDS: Nanocomposite, Nanotube, MD simulation, Molecular interaction, Interfacial bonding

INTRODUCTION

SWNTs have remarkable characteristics, such as novel electronic properties, exceptionally high strength and axial Young's modulus of 1TPa. Coupled with defect-free molecular structures, they are considered the ideal reinforcements for next generation of high performance composites and the new materials will create revolutionary properties for use in wide applications [1-3]. However, the very high chemical stability of nanotube fullerene structure makes wetting by polymer materials during nanotube composite processing difficult. Several research groups have fabricated nanotube-polymer composites by the solution casting technique. In their studies, epoxy resins and thermoplastic polymers were used as the matrix polymers. Schadler et al. [4] observed a 20% increase in both tensile and compressive moduli of an epoxy upon ultrasonically dispersing 5wt.% multi-walled nanotubes (MWNTs) in the EPON 828 epoxy resin. Qian et al. [5] studied composite films in which MWNTs were dispersed in a polystyrene matrix. They reported a 1wt.% nanotube addition resulted in 36-42% increase in elastic modulus and a 25% increase in break stress. The research results have shown that composite materials made by direct mixing of

nanotubes and polymeric resin do not demonstrate the much-anticipated performance. The poor wetting and weak interfacial bonding are considered major reasons for this shortcoming. New principles and techniques are needed to understand and investigate such nano-scale processing phenomena in nanotube-based composites [6-9].

In this study, MD simulations were carried out to explore the interactions between (10,10) SWNTs and EPI-CURE W curing agent (DETA), and DGEBA (diglycidylether of bisphenol A) resin/diethylenetriamine/DETDA curing agent molecules. A three-dimensional cross-link model of the cured resin was established for MD simulation of a single SWNT pullout to predict the interfacial bonding properties of the resultant composites. Preliminary experimental results of the wetting and interfacial bonding of the composites were also compared to the MD simulation results. Molecular dynamics simulations were carried out on a SGI-Octane2 workstation using Materials Studio, a commercial software package developed by Accelrys, Inc. The condensed phase optimization molecular potentials for atomistic simulation studies (COMPASS) module in the Materials Studio software was used to conduct force field computations. The COMPASS was parameterized, tested and validated for most of the common organic and inorganic materials [10,11]. This method was parameterized from *ab initio* computations of model compounds and optimized using condensed-phase properties of polymers and low-molecular-weight compounds. All calculations were carried out at the initial temperature of 300 K, using NVT ensembles constant number of particles, constant volume and constant temperature.

MOLECULAR INTERACTIONS BETWEEN (10,10) SWNT AND THE RESIN AND CURING AGENT MOLECULES

Molecular Model of (10,10) SWNT The molecular model of a (10, 10) SWNT was established using Materials Studio. The electronic structure of all carbon atoms in the SWNT model was sp² hybridization. The modeled SWNT had a finite length of 2.71nm with a diameter of 1.38nm. The SWNT model is shown in Figure 1. The unsaturated boundary effect was avoided by adding 20 hydrogen atoms at each end of the carbon nanotube. The model had 400 carbon atoms and 40 hydrogen atoms. The hydrogen atoms had charges of +0.1268e, and the carbon atoms connecting the hydrogen atoms had charges of -0.1268e, thus the carbon nanotube was neutrally charged.

Figure 1. Molecular model of (10,10) SWNT

Molecular Models of EPON 862 Resin and EPI-CURE Curing Agent W Epon 862 was selected as resin matrix due to its low processing viscosity and good comprehensive mechanical properties for composite applications. The molecular model of Epon 862 resin oligomer is shown in Figure 2(a). Energy-minimization molecular mechanics were performed using Materials Studio to find the thermal stable morphology and achieve a conformation with minimum potential energy for the Epon 862 resin molecule. This minimum energy conformation of the molecule was

used as initial status in the MD computation. Under this minimum energy, the molecule had the approximate dimensions of $23 \text{ \AA} \times 9 \text{ \AA} \times 6 \text{ \AA}$, which can be estimated in the software. The major ingredient of EPI-CURE Curing Agent W is diethyltoluenediamine (DETDA), an aromatic amine-curing agent. The molecular model of DETDA is given in Figure 2(b). Under the minimum energy, the dimensions of DETDA molecule were $6.7 \text{ \AA} \times 6.5 \text{ \AA} \times 1.8 \text{ \AA}$.

Figure 2. Molecular models of Epon 862 and DETDA molecules

Molecular Models of DGEBA Resin/DETA Curing Agent In order to compare with the Epon 862/DETDA system, another very popular epoxy system was also used in the research. DGEBA resin oligomer has a relative long molecular chain with bisphenol-A structure. Its molecular model under the minimum energy was calculated and provided in Figure 3(a). At this minimum energy, the DGEBA molecule has a saddle-shape and the dimensions of the molecule were $38 \text{ \AA} \times 10 \text{ \AA} \times 6 \text{ \AA}$. Unlike DETDA, DETA is an aliphatic amine curing agent. At the minimum energy, the DETA molecule's dimensions were $8 \text{ \AA} \times 4 \text{ \AA} \times 3 \text{ \AA}$, as shown in Figure 3(b).

Figure 3. Molecular models of DGEBA and DETA molecules

Molecular Interactions between SWNT and Epon 862 Molecule Snapshots of the MD simulations of the interactions between (10,10) SWNT and Epon 862 molecule are shown in Figure 4. Initially, the chain of Epon 862 resin molecule was twisted under a minimum energy status. One end of the chain was put near the nanotube's wall, while the other end was placed away from the nanotube. The simulation shows that during the initial 16ps, the molecular chain of the Epon 862 resin stretched and moved toward the nanotube. All atoms in the resin molecule gradually moved towards the nanotube's wall. After a long equilibration period of 100ps, the resin molecule chain eventually tended to spirally wrap on the surface of the nanotube. The nanotube maintained its overall shape, although some distortion of its cross section occurred during the interaction. As shown in Figure 4, two aromatic rings of the molecule finally orientated to align their ring plane parallel to the SWNT surface. The negative interaction energy of the MD simulation indicates that the EPON 862 epoxy resin molecule moved towards the nanotube's surface due to an attractive force. The interaction energy of the SWNT and the EPON 862 epoxy resin molecules was decreased by 25 kcal/mol based on the MD simulation result.

Figure 4. MD simulation snapshots of SWNT/Epon 862 interactions

Molecular Interactions between SWNT and DETDA The MD simulations of the interactions between SWNT and DETDA molecule were conducted using the same procedure. The MD simulation results are provided in Figure 5. The DETDA molecule also tried to orient its aromatic ring plane to face the SWNT surface and move closer to the SWNT to achieve a low potential energy status, which indicated that the DETDA molecule also had an attractive interaction with the SWNT.

Molecular Interactions between SWNT and DGEBA Molecule The results of the MD simulation of SWNT and DGEBA interactions are given in Figure 6. As with the Epon 862 molecule, the DGEBA molecule changed its original conformation and gradually moved toward the nanotube wall due to the attractive interactions. Unlike the EPON 862 epoxy resin, the DGEBA molecule wrapped the nanotube surface with a more twisted molecular chain conformation in order to reach a minimum energy state. The molecular conformation change and attractive tendency of DGEBA during the intercalations are shown in Figure 11. The attractive interaction energy between the SWNT and DGEBA was about 60 kcal/mol, higher than that of SWNT/Epon 862 interaction since more atoms were involved. Good wetting between SWNT and DGEBA was found to be favorable according to this MD simulation result.

Figure 5. MD simulation snapshots of SWNT/DETDA interactions

(a) Ortho view snapshot

(b) Top view snapshot

Figure 6. MD simulation snapshots of SWNT/DGEBA interactions

Molecular Interactions between SWNT and DETA The MD simulations of the interactions between SWNT and DETDA molecule were carried out in this research. The MD simulation results are provided in Figure 7. It can be seen that the DETDA molecule tried to move towards to the SWNT surface and move closer to the SWNT to achieve a low potential energy status due to the van der Waals interaction. Different from DETDA molecule, there is no aromatic ring in the DETA molecular structure and therefore the molecule does not show any preferred orientation movement during the interactions.

Figure 7. MD simulation snapshots of SWNT/DETA interactions

MD SIMULATION OF SINGLE SWNT PULLOUT FROM SWNT/ CURED EPON 862/DETDA NANOCOMPOSITES

In order to theoretically predict interfacial bonding strength of the SWNT/epoxy composite, a molecular model of a single SWNT/cured Epon 862/DETDA matrix was established as shown in Figure 8. In the model, the matrix density around the SWNT tube was 1.2 g/cm^3 and model dimensions were $50 \text{ \AA} \times 50 \text{ \AA} \times 100 \text{ \AA}$, having total 21,288 atoms. No chemical bonding between the tube and resin matrix was included in the model. In this study, a simplified and fast computational pullout approach was applied to obtain the interaction energy change during the SWNT pullout by directly calculating the system potential energy at different tube pullout stages. The various stages of the tube pullout are shown in Figure 9. The system potential energy increase during the tube pullout was monitored during the tube pullout. At the initial stage (before tube pullout), the potential energy of the composite was 152,665 kcal/mol. After the complete tube pullout ($\Delta Z = 110 \text{ \AA}$), the potential energy increased to 154,951 kcal/mol. The increase of the potential energy is mainly due to the creation of a new surface and the molecular interaction changes between the tube and resin matrix in the material system. Furthermore, the increase of the potential energy can be used to estimate the interfacial shear strength between the tube and the resin matrix [12]. The estimated interfacial shear strength of the SWNT/epoxy composite is about 75 MPa, which is about 20%~80% higher than that of most carbon fiber reinforced composites [13]. Such high interfacial shear strength could be attributed to high surface area/volume ratio of well-dispersed individual SWNTs embedded in the resin matrix in the computation model.

Figure 8. Molecular model of single SWNT/epoxy nanocomposite

$\Delta Z = 0 \text{ \AA}$	$\Delta Z = 25 \text{ \AA}$	$\Delta Z = 50 \text{ \AA}$
$\Delta Z = 75 \text{ \AA}$	$\Delta Z = 90 \text{ \AA}$	$\Delta Z = 110 \text{ \AA}$

Figure 9. Different stages of tube pullout (ΔZ is pullout distance)

EXPERIMENTAL OBSERVATIONS

SWNTs-reinforced Epon 862/DETDA resin matrix composites with a high SWNT loading (25w/w%-47w/w%) was fabricated using SWNT buckypapers/resin infiltration process developed by the authors [14]. The SWNTs used in this study were BuckyPearls™, purified SWNTs from Carbon Nanotechnologies, Inc. (CNI), Houston, TX. The nanostructure of the resulting composite is shown in Figures 10 and 11. Some resin adhesion on the tube surface at the failure cross-section of the resultant composites as arrows indicate in Figure 10. AFM observation of the cross-section of the nanocomposites also shows that the surface of SWNTs or their ropes are well covered by the Epon 862 resin as show in Figure 11. These observations show that the selected resin matrix has a good tendency of wetting and bonding SWNTs, which agrees with our MD simulation results.

Figure 10. Tube/resin bonding at

Figure 11 Epon 862 matrix covered on

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, MD simulation was used to understand and assess the molecular interactions during tube/resin wetting and interfacial bonding of the resultant SWNT/epoxy resin composites. The simulation results show that the molecules of Epon 862, DGEBA and DETDA will change the molecular conformation and try to align their aromatic ring parallel to the surface of (10,10) SWNT due to π -stacking effect. As a result, these molecules could stretch and wrap on the surface of the SWNT, whereas DETA molecule does not aromatic ring and there is no such tendency observed in the simulation. The simulation results show that the interfacial shear strength could be as high as 75Mpa for a single SWNT pullout from the cured resin matrix in the SWNT/Epon 862 resin nanocomposites due to only van der Waals interactions. Based on the MD simulations, Epon 862 resin/EPI-CURE W curing agent system was used to fabricate SWNT/epoxy composite samples. The microscopic observations also showed some good wetting between SWNT and Epon 862 resin system, which preliminarily validated the MD simulation results.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research is sponsored by the Air Force Research Laboratory (Grant #: F08630-01-1-0010), the NSF-IUCRC Program (Award #: 0224612) and Florida State University Cornerstone Research Program.

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